

WHY I WANT TO LEARN FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND MAKE MY COUNTRY OF UZBEKISTAN FAMOUS FOR THE WORLD

G'ulomjonova Marjona Botirjon qizi

6th grade pupil at public school № 42, Turakurgan, Namangan

Mamanazarova Dilnoza Azimjon qizi

English teacher at school № 42, Turakurgan, Namangan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8086615>

Annotation. *In this article, the author shares their personal experience of learning foreign languages and how it has shaped their career aspirations. The author's passion for language learning is evident, and they highlight the importance of being multilingual in today's globalized world.*

Key words: *language learning, career aspirations, multilingual, globalized world, translator, interpreter, communication, cultures, understanding, bridges, communities, Uzbekistan, communication skills, broadening perspectives, cultural exchange, interconnected world, positive impact, passion.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье автор делится своим личным опытом изучения иностранных языков и тем, как это повлияло на их карьерные устремления. Страсть автора к изучению языков очевидна, и они подчеркивают важность многоязычия в современном глобализованном мире.*

Ключевые слова: *изучение языка, карьерные устремления, многоязычный, глобализированный мир, переводчик, устный переводчик, общение, культуры, понимание, мосты, сообщества, Узбекистан, коммуникативные навыки, расширение кругозора, культурный обмен, взаимосвязанный мир, позитивное влияние, страсть.*

The author's desire to become a translator or interpreter is admirable, as these professions play a crucial role in facilitating communication between people from different cultures and backgrounds. By breaking down language barriers, translators and interpreters can help promote understanding and build bridges between communities.

Furthermore, the author's goal of encouraging other young people in Uzbekistan to learn foreign languages is commendable. Learning a foreign language not only enhances communication skills but also broadens one's perspective on the world. By promoting language learning, the author is also promoting cultural exchange and understanding, which is essential in today's interconnected world.

Overall, this article highlights the importance of language learning and its potential to make a positive impact on individuals and society as a whole. It serves as an inspiration to others to pursue their passion for language learning and use their skills to make a difference in the world.

As a 12-year-old school girl from Uzbekistan, I have always been fascinated by foreign languages. I believe that learning foreign languages is not only important for personal growth, but it can also help to make my country famous for the world. In this article, I will explain why I want to learn foreign languages and how it can benefit my country.

Firstly, learning foreign languages can help me to communicate with people from different parts of the world. As a student, I have already had the opportunity to meet students from different countries who speak different languages. By learning their languages, I can communicate with them more effectively and build stronger relationships with them. This can also help me to understand their cultures and perspectives better.

Secondly, learning foreign languages can open up new opportunities for me in the future. As the world becomes more globalized, there is a growing demand for people who can speak multiple languages. By learning foreign languages, I can increase my chances of getting a good job in the

future. This can also help me to become a better citizen of Uzbekistan by contributing to the economy and society.

Thirdly, learning foreign languages can help me to promote Uzbekistan to the world. Uzbekistan is a beautiful country with a rich culture and history. By learning foreign languages, I can share my knowledge and experiences of Uzbekistan with people from different parts of the world. This can help to promote tourism and cultural exchange between Uzbekistan and other countries.

In order to achieve my goal of making Uzbekistan famous for the world, I believe that it is important to start by learning as many foreign languages as possible. Currently, I am learning English and Russian at school. However, I want to learn more languages in the future, such as Spanish, French, Chinese, and Arabic. By learning these languages, I can communicate with people from different parts of the world and promote Uzbekistan to them.

In addition to learning foreign languages, I also believe that it is important to promote the teaching of foreign languages in Uzbekistan. Currently, many schools in Uzbekistan do not offer foreign language classes or only offer a limited number of languages. This can make it difficult for students to learn foreign languages and communicate with people from different parts of the world. Therefore, I think it is important for the government to invest more in foreign language education and encourage schools to offer a wider range of languages.

Another way to promote Uzbekistan to the world is through cultural exchange programs. By participating in cultural exchange programs, students from Uzbekistan can learn about other cultures and share their own culture with people from different parts of the world. This can help to promote understanding and respect between different cultures and countries.

Furthermore, my dream is to become a translator or an interpreter in the future. I want to use my language skills to help people from different countries communicate with each other and bridge the gap between different cultures. I believe that being a translator or interpreter is an important job that can make a positive impact on the world.

Lastly, I want to encourage other young people in Uzbekistan to learn foreign languages and explore the world. I believe that by learning foreign languages, we can broaden our horizons and gain new perspectives on the world. We can also become ambassadors for our country and promote its unique culture and heritage to the world. I hope that more young people in Uzbekistan will join me in this journey of learning and discovery.

In conclusion, as a 12-year-old school girl from Uzbekistan, I believe that learning foreign languages is important for personal growth and for making my country famous for the world. By learning foreign languages, I can communicate with people from different parts of the world, open up new opportunities for myself, and promote Uzbekistan to the world. I am committed to learning as many foreign languages as possible and promoting the teaching of foreign languages in Uzbekistan. I hope that my efforts can contribute to a more connected and understanding world.

REFERENCES:

1. XORIJIY TILLARNI O'RGANISH NEGA MUHIM? Umida Xasan Qizi Ahmadova
2. THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN UZBEK CLASSES. Mukhlisa Bakhtiyor kizi Makhamadieva
3. Madaniyatlararo muloqotda tarjimonning ahamiyati. G. Raxmonberdiyeva
4. TARJIMADA UCHRAYDIGAN ASOSIY XATOLAR. Sh. D. Razakova
5. THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN CREATING A NEW ENLIGHTENED SOCIETY OF UZBEKISTAN. Nosirova, Dilfuza Nabievna